

"CORRELATION AND PATH COEFFICIENT ANALYSIS OF YIELD AND YIELD COMPONENTS IN AMARANTHUS

[*Amaranthus hypochondriacus* (L.)]"B. H. Kale¹, S. B. Sarode¹, S. S. Gomashe², S. L. Haloli¹ and S. G. Gawai¹¹Department of Agricultural Botany, College of Agriculture, Badnapur,
VNMKV Parbhani – 431202 (India)²ICAR- National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, Regional Station, Akola (M.S.)
shrisarode24@gmail.com

(MS Received: 26.01.2024; MS Revised:28.02.2024; MS Accepted:01.03.2024)

MS 3169

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL PROCESSING AND FOOD ENGINEERING)

Abstract:

In the present study, correlation and path coefficient analysis with 10 yield and yield attributing characters was carried out in one hundred fifty germplasm and three standard checks of grain *Amaranthus* replicated twice in Randomized Block Design with 2 replications at college of Agriculture Badnapur during kharif, 2017. Seed yield per plant had significant positive association with days to 50% flowering, plant height, number of primary branches per plant, number of secondary branches per plant, stem diameter, inflorescence length, days to maturity, thousand grain weight, seed yield per plant and protein content. Positive direct effect on seed yield per plant were observed for days to 50 per cent flowering, number of secondary branches per plant, stem diameter, inflorescence length, days to maturity, thousand grain weight, seed yield per plant and protein content. These traits should be taken into consideration in breeding high yielding varieties in grain amaranthus through selection.

Key words: *Amaranthus*, correlation, genotypic, phenotypic, path coefficient, direct effect, indirect effect.

Introduction

Grain *Amaranthus* also known as *Rajgira* or pigweed belongs to family Amaranthaceae trib Amranthaceae subfamily Amaranthoideae suborder chenopodiaceae Goosefoot family chenopodiaceae and common name Rajgira or pigweed. It is a self pollinated, tetraploid ($2n = 36$) crop. Grain *Amaranthus* (*Amaranthus hypochondriacus* L.) are important pseudocereals that are widely cultivated in India in the sub-Himalayan ranges and in the Nilgiri Hills of South India. The long history of cultivation of grain amaranthus in India under diverse agro-climatic conditions and the associated human and natural selection has resulted in generation of large variability giving India the status of secondary centre of diversity. The first advance estimation area, production and productivity in Maharashtra kharif 2017-2018 total area 0.864 lakh ha, production 0.932 lakh tones and productivity 1078 kg/ha (Directorate of Agriculture, Government of Maharashtra). In India amaranth is cultivated in Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Sikkim, Assam, Meghalaya, Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Tripura, Jharkhand, Chattisgarh, Maharashtra, Gujrat, Orissa, Karnataka, Kerala and Tamil Nadu both in hills and plains. The exact information about the statistics on area and production in India is lacking. However, as a grain crop it is estimated to be grown in about 40-50 thousands ha. Hand harvested yields have been as high as 4000 kg/ha in Montana and 6000 kg/ha in Peru, between 2500 and 3300 kg/ha in southwest Germany, between 2100 and 2700 kg/ha in Slovak Republic and 1200 kg/ha in India.

Material and Methods

The experimental material comprising in one hundred fifty germplasm and three standard checks of grain *Amaranthus* replicated twice were grown during during kharif, 2017 in Randomized Block Design with 2 replications at College of Agriculture Badnapur, Section of Agricultural Botany, The data were recorded on five randomly tagged plant. Genetic advance as per cent of mean ranged from 16.33 to 79.69. Seed yield per plant had significant positive association with days to 50% flowering, plant height, number of primary branches per plant, number of secondary branches per plant, stem diameter, inflorescence length, days to maturity, thousand grain weight, seed yield per plant and protein content. Positive direct effect on seed yield per plant were observed for days to 50 per cent flowering, number of secondary branches per plant, stem diameter, inflorescence length, days to maturity, thousand grain weight, seed yield per plant and protein content. These traits should be taken into consideration in breeding high yielding varieties in grain *Amaranthus* through selection.

Result And Discussion

In any crop improvement programme, knowledge on the association of characters is of significant importance since it contributes indirectly to the success of selection. Yield is considered to be a dependent variable on several sub components. In such cases, knowledge of the nature of association between such characters is a great asset for plant breeders to formulate their breeding procedures. It has been suggested that yield might be more effectively increased simultaneously improving one or more yield components (Aruna *et al.*, 2009).

Correlation coefficients

The correlation study was undertaken in 150 genotypes of grain *Amaranthus* in order to find out interrelation of different yield components at genotypic and phenotypic level. The genotypic and phenotypic correlation coefficient for ten characters as presented in Table 1 & 2 respectively. The correlation studies in the present investigation revealed seed yield per plant had significant positive association with days to maturity ($p = 0.4960$; $g = 0.5115$), number of secondary branches per plant ($p = 0.4809$; $g = 0.5194$), inflorescence length ($p = 0.4113$; $g = 0.4248$), thousand grain weight ($p = 0.3181$; $g = 0.3674$), number of primary branches per plant ($p = 0.2416$; $g = 0.2708$), days to 50% flowering ($p = 0.2303$; $g = 0.2358$) and stem diameter ($p = 0.1799$; $g = 0.2579$). The results suggested that any positive increase in these traits will accelerate the yield potential of grain amaranth. So, these traits should be paid attention in grain amaranth breeding programmes. In the present investigation the phenotypic coefficient of variation was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variation for all the traits this indicates that there is small effect of environment on characters and selection may be effective. Although range can provide a preliminary idea about the variability, coefficient of variation is reliable, as it is independent of unit measurement. The extent of variability as measured by GCV and PCV also gives information regarding relative amount of variation in different populations. The GCV and PCV showed wide variation for most of the characters. As expected the PCV was invariably higher than GCV for all the characters. GCV and PCV values were categorized as low (0-10%), moderate (10-20) and high (20% and above). The value for GCV ranged from 8.06 to 39.61 per cent. Similar observations were observed by Pawar (1995), Venkatesh *et al.*, (2013) and Yadav *et al.* (2014). Similar observations were observed for days to 50 per cent by Akaneme and Ani (2013), for stem diameter by Vekatesh *et al.* (2013), for inflorescence length by Joshi (1986), Venkatesh *et al.* (2013) and Yadav *et al.* (2014), for character 1000 seed weight by Joshi (1986) and Akaneme and Ani (2013), for days to maturity by Joshi (1986) and

Aruah *et al.*, (2012), for protein content by Venkatesh *et al.* (2013) and for plant height by Venkatesh *et al.* (2013).

Path coefficient analysis

Correlation coefficients indicate only the general association between any two traits without possible causes of such association. Path coefficient analysis presents a better idea of cause-and-effect relationship among different characters and plays an important role in determining the degree of relationship between the yield and yield components. Therefore, the path coefficient analysis was performed to partition the correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effect of different characters on yield.

Branches per plant and 100 seed weight by Shukla *et al.* (2010), for plant height and for providing germplasm of *Amaranthus*. To find out the direct and indirect contribution from each of the characters towards seed yield per plant, path coefficient analysis was carried out. The genotypic correlation coefficients being more important are only partitioned to direct and indirect effects which are presented in Table 3. It is evident from the data presented in Table 3 that positive direct effect on seed yield per plant were observed for days to 50% flowering, number of secondary branches per plant, stem diameter, inflorescence length, days to maturity, thousand grain weight, and protein content. These traits should be taken into consideration inflorescence length by Maruthi *et al.* (1987), for plant height Shukla and Singh (2003), for days to maturity by Patial *et al.* (2014), for protein content by Tejaswini *et al.* (2017). Negative indirect effect on seed yield per plant was recorded by character inflorescence length similar results were obtained by Shukla and Singh (2003).

Acknowledgement:

ICAR- National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources, New Delhi for providing germplasm lines of *Amaranthus*.

References

1. **Akaneme, F.I and Ani, G.O., 2013.** Morphological assessment of genetic variability among accessions of *amaranthus hybridus* world applied sciences journal **28** (4): 568-577.
2. **Aruna P. 2009.** Correlation and path analysis in amaranthus. *The Asian Journal of Horticulture*. **4** (2): 361-363.
3. **Joshi, B.D., 1986.** Genetic variability in grain amaranth, *Amaranthus hypochondriacus* Linn. *Indian J. Agric. Sci.* **56** : 574 – 576.
4. **S. J. Keraliya¹, L. J. Desai², S. J. Patel³, D. A. Kanara⁴ 2017,** Effect Of Integrated Nitrogen Management On Growth And Yield Of Grain Amaranth (*Amaranthus Hypochondriacus* L.) Under South Gujarat Condition, Vol. Vii, Issue Xxiii, July 2017 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 89-91.
5. **B. B. Mali*, 1 p. B. Wadikar, 1 a. S. Gorte And 1 u. V. Yadav, 2022,** Relationships Among Traits Using Correlation And Path Coefficient Analysis In Safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius* L.) Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxxii, April 2022 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 79-82.

6. **Maruthi, 1987.** Seasonal evaluation of genetic variability, character association and diversity studies in Grain Amaranth (*Amaranthus spp.*). M. Sc (Agri), *Thesis, Univ. Agric. Sci.*, Bangalore, 125.
7. **Patial, M., Chauhan, A., Singh, K.P. and Sharma, D., 2014.** Character Association and Path Coefficient Analysis in Grain Amaranth (*Amaranthus spp.*) *IJAEB*: **6**(1): 101-106.
8. **Pawar, A.N., 1995.** Genetic diversity and path analysis in amaranthus. M.Sc. (Agri.). thesis submitted to M.P.K.V., Rahuri.
9. **R.Eswaran*,K.R. Saravanan And P.Karthikeyan 2019,** Correlation And Path Coefficient Analysis In Cotton, Vol. Viii, Issue Xxviii, Jan 2019 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 223-225.
10. **Shweta, Vaibhav Singh, R.K. Yadav, Sarvendra Gupta and Geeta Rai 2018** Correlation And Path Coefficient Analysis Of Yield And Yield Associated Traits In Field Pea (*Pisum sativum* var. arvense.) Germplasm , Vol. Viii, Special Issue (A) August-2018 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 22-25.
11. **Shukla, S. and Singh, S.P., 2003.** Correlation and path analysis in Grain Amaranth (*Amaranthus spp.*). *Indian J. Genet.*, **63**: 136-164.
12. **Shukla, S., Bhargava, A., Chatterjee, A., Pandey, A.C., Rastogi, A. and Kumar, A., 2010.** Genetic interrelationship among nutritional and quantitative traits in the vegetable amaranth *Crop Breeding and Applied Biotechnology* **10**: 16-22.
13. **Tejaswini, N., Reddy, R. K., Saidaiah, P. and Ramesh, T., 2017.** Correlation and Path Coefficient Analysis in Vegetable Amaranth (*Amaranthus tricolor*L.) Genotypes *Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci* **6** (6): 2977-2996.
14. **Venkatesh, L., Murthy, N., Manjappa and Nehru, S.D., 2014.** Character association and path co-efficient analysis for various traits in grain amaranth (*Amaranthus spp.*) *Asian Journal of Bio Science*, **9** (1) 97-100.
15. **Venkatesh, Murthy, N., Nehru, S.D. and Manjappa., 2013.** Genetic variability, heritability and genetic advance in grain amaranth (*Amaranthus spp.*) *Asian Journal of Bio Science*, **9** (1), 67-70.
16. **Vikas Khandelwal 2019,** Correlation And Path Coefficient Analysis For Agronomical Traits In Sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench] Over The Environments, Vol. Ix, Issue Xxxi, Oct 2019 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, PP 230-237.
17. **Yadav, R., Rana, J.C. and Ranjan, J.K., 2014.** Analysis of variability parameters for morphological and agronomic traits in grain amaranth (*Amaranthus spp.*) genotypes *an international quarterly journal of life science*.

Table 1. Estimation of genotypic (above diagonal) correlation coefficients in Grain Amaranthus.

SN	Days to 50 % flowering	Plant height (cm)	Primary branches per plant	Secondary branches per plant	Stem diameter (cm)	Inflorescence length (cm)	Days to maturity	Thousand grain weight (g)	Protein content (%)	Seed yield per plant (g)
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	1.0000	0.0454	0.1746**	0.2298**	0.1395*	0.3380**	0.1706**	0.1169	0.3049**	0.2358**
2		1.0000	0.1312*	0.0910	0.0525	0.1873**	0.1360*	0.2066**	0.3126**	0.0097
3			1.0000	0.5448**	0.2672**	0.1459**	0.3102**	0.1515	0.3881**	0.2708**
4				1.0000	0.2379**	0.1858**	0.5394**	0.4038**	0.5791**	0.5194**
5					1.0000	0.3652**	0.2858**	0.0175	0.2298**	0.2579**
6						1.0000	0.4247**	0.2403**	0.3557**	0.4248**
7							1.0000	0.3169**	0.5399**	0.5115**
8								1.0000	0.3752**	0.3674**
9									1.0000	0.4883**
10										1.0000

* Significant at 5 % and ** Significant at 1 % level of probability or level of significanc

Table 2. Estimation of phenotypic (above diagonal) correlation coefficients in grain Amaranthus.

SN	Days to 50 % flowering	Plant height (cm)	Primary branches per plant	Secondary branches per plant	Stem diameter (cm)	Inflorescence length (cm)	Days to maturity	Thousand grain weight (g)	Seed yield per plant	Protein content (%)
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	1.0000	0.0454	0.1574**	0.2108**	0.1034	0.3298**	0.1649**	0.1088	0.2303**	0.2936**
2		1.0000	0.1231*	0.0848	0.0401	0.1871**	0.1352*	0.1861*	0.0137	0.3013**
3			1.0000	0.4904**	0.1827**	0.1289*	0.2818**	0.1298	0.2416**	0.3472**
4				1.0000	0.1722**	0.1749**	0.5100**	0.3470**	0.4809**	0.5462**
5					1.0000	0.2400**	0.1856**	0.0076	0.1799**	0.1600**
6						1.0000	0.4182**	0.2202**	0.4113**	0.3442**
7							1.0000	0.2845**	0.4960**	0.5168**
8								1.0000	0.3181**	0.3435**
9									1.0000	0.4588**
10										1.0000

* Significant at 5 % and ** Significant at 1 % level of probability or level of significance,

Table. 3 Direct and indirect effect of ten causal variables on seed yield in Grain Amaranthus.

SN	Days to 50 % flowering	Plant height (cm)	Primary branches per plant	Secondary branches per plant	Stem diameter (cm)	Inflorescence length (cm)	Days to maturity	Thousand grain weight (g)	Protein content(%)	correlation with seed yield/plant(g)
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	0.0100	0.0005	0.0017	0.0023	0.0014	0.0034	0.0017	0.0012	0.0031	0.2358
2		-0.1575	-0.0207	-0.0143	-0.0083	-0.0295	-0.0214	-0.0325	-0.0492	0.0097
3			-0.0312	-0.0170	-0.0083	-0.0045	-0.0097	-0.0047	-0.0121	0.2708
4				0.2606	0.0620	0.0484	0.1405	0.1052	0.1509	0.5194
5					0.0391	0.0143	0.0112	0.0007	0.0090	0.2579
6						0.2348	0.0997	0.0564	0.0835	0.4248
7							0.1570	0.0498	0.0848	0.5115
8								0.1273	0.0478	0.3674
9									0.1707	0.4883
10										

Residual effect = 0.7850, Underlined figures indicate direct effect.

*, ** indicates significant at 5 and 1 % level of significant respective

Fig.1. Genotypical correlation in grain amaranthus.

Fig.2 Diagram showing the genotypic correlation in yield and its component characters of Grain Amaranthus

